

Using Collaborative Technologies to Increase the Responsibility of Teachers and Parents for the Health-Preserving Education of Children

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 02 Feb 2025; **Accepted:** 03 Mar 2025; **Published:** 09 Apr 2025

Abstract: The article examines current issues of modern pedagogy - the role of collaborative technologies in increasing the responsibility of teachers and parents for the health-preserving education of children.

Keys words: Collaboration, collaborative technologies, responsibility, health, health-preserving education.

As is known, collaboration is a cooperation aimed at achieving a goal by combining knowledge, experience and resources to solve complex problems and achieve effective results [1]. The modern educational system requires a new approach to interaction between teachers and parents, since raising children can no longer be viewed as an exclusively school or family responsibility - it is necessary to combine efforts to create a single environment for the child's development. As is known, collaborative approaches allow you to build an effective system of cooperation, increasing the responsibility of both parties for the educational and upbringing process and increasing children's health-preserving competence. In the context of the above, responsibility should be considered as "a form of self-regulation of the individual, expressed in the awareness of oneself as the cause of the actions committed and their consequences and the awareness and control of one's ability to act as the cause of changes (or counteraction to changes) in the surrounding world and in one's own life" [2, p. 477]. At the same time, a very important form of responsibility is social responsibility - a person's tendency to behave in accordance with the interests of other people and the social whole, and not in narrowly selfish interests, to adhere to accepted norms, in particular in matters of preserving the health of both oneself and others.

According to researchers, a sense of responsibility should be cultivated from an early age, mainly by encouraging the child's independence in making decisions, including how to maintain and strengthen health and ensure life safety. Responsibility for health preservation is formed as a result of the requirements that are imposed on the individual, being the internal basis for motivation of behavior. Upon entering school, there is a need for new or more advanced responsible qualities of the individual: discipline, consciousness, organization, self-exactingness, etc. The achievement of these goals is successfully facilitated by the use of collaborative technologies that help increase the responsibility of teachers and parents for improving the health preservation of students [3].

It has been established that the introduction of collaborative technologies, enhancing their influence on teachers and parents, is the definition of the concept of "collaborative technologies" and their role in education.

According to the literature, collaborative technologies are methods and tools aimed at organizing joint work of participants in the educational process (teachers and parents) to achieve common goals, including ensuring the health of students: digital platforms for interaction; joint decision-making; interactive forms of communication; project and role-playing methods dedicated to solving issues of protecting the health of students, in educating them about the main components of a healthy lifestyle [4].

The systematic use of collaborative technologies in the field of education allows for the establishment of an effective partnership between school and family, increasing the responsibility of both parties for the comprehensive development and health of the child.

It should be noted that the collaborative approach is based on the following principles: unity of goals - parents and teachers work in the interests of the child; transparency of interaction - timely information about the child's achievements and difficulties; equal partnership - rejection of the traditional model of "teacher-mentor - parent-listener"; interactivity - the use of modern health-saving technologies for active communication and discussion of problems of strengthening the health of students.

Constant adherence to these principles ensures high-quality interaction and a higher level of responsibility of both parties. Collaborative technologies are currently being actively implemented - technologies for building and supporting a collaborative space, which is a set of jointly created artifacts and ways for collaboration participants to access them. The use of collaborative technologies to increase the responsibility of teachers and parents for health-preserving education of students is an interactive process in which education is carried out with close interaction between students, teachers and parents, aimed at developing health-preserving consciousness and thinking, creating a health-preserving environment, organizing health-preserving activities, developing health-preserving competence and health philosophy and a positive attitude towards a healthy lifestyle and ensuring life safety. These technologies include: project-based, problem-based, discussion-based, game-based, training, development of critical thinking, development of global thinking. Collaborative technologies significantly affect the increase in the responsibility of teachers and parents. At the same time, in the context of influencing teachers, the use of collaborative technologies allows: to form trusting relationships with parents; to provide feedback and adjust working methods; to perform a certain part of educational functions; to take into account the individual needs of each specific child.

At the same time, collaborative technologies involve parents in the educational process, promoting: awareness of their role in education; increasing the level of pedagogical competence; participation in the life of the school and a sense of real results; increasing their responsibility for the quality of health care of students.

At the current stage of development of society, the role of information technologies in cooperation between teachers and parents in the context of increasing their responsibility for the health of students is very significant. The following digital tools have received recognition:

- electronic diaries and educational platforms (Dnevnik.ru, MESH, Google Classroom) - allow parents to quickly receive data on academic performance and attendance and judge the level of activity and performance of students;
- chats and online forums (WhatsApp, Telegram, school platforms) - facilitating the dissemination of information about health potential, factors influencing various types of health;
- video conferences (Zoom, Microsoft Teams) — providing the opportunity for parents to participate in meetings and discussions of health-preserving activities of participants in educational institutions. The use of digital tools allows parents and teachers to be in constant contact, which forms a more responsible attitude to the process of health-preserving education [5].

Creative communication between teachers and parents is an important element of collaboration, enhancing the educational effect through family and school trainings - educational programs for parents aimed at developing their health-preserving literacy.

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